

Causes and Consequences of Female Migration in Khorezm Region

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Abstract: Today, in the process of ever-expanding migration, the share of women is also increasing. This article aims to reveal the causes and indicators of women's migration in the Khorezm region, their negative impact on the family and child upbringing. The methods of analysis and synthesis, scientific abstraction, systematic and comparative analysis, chronological analysis, monographic observation, and field research were used in writing the study. During the field study, interviews were conducted with responsible officials in 10 districts on the topic. Their conclusions were used to illuminate the topic. Previously, women participated in migration as partners, but now they are looking to earn money as the main breadwinners. However, it was found that women's migration has more negative consequences for families and children than men's migration. In the Khorezm region, the largest share of women's migration abroad is occupied by women aged 30 to 45. This means that the migration of women of childbearing age and mothers with children is high. This affects the upbringing of children in the family, and changes in the educational environment in the family also change the moral and educational environment in society.

Keywords: labor migration, feminism, women's migration, economic factor, environmental factor, social factor.

Introduction.

Population migration has been a historical companion of development in all eras. Since the era of the great geographical discoveries, it has been taking place on a large scale.[1] Migration is broadly defined as a permanent or semi-permanent change of place of residence. [2] The number of immigrants in the world is increasing from year to year, for example, from 75 million in 1965 to 120 million in 1990, and to 190 million in 2006.[3] In the 1980s, the role of external migration in population growth was on average 25 percent in countries such as the USA, Canada, France, and Australia. In other words, immigrants accounted for a quarter of the population growth in these countries. [4] Today, labor migration occupies a major place in international migration. Because modern times have increased the importance of the economic factor for human survival. Labor migration is the movement of individuals from one country to another or within them for employment. [5]The share of women in this type of migration is increasing, that is, the feminization of migration is observed. Structural changes in the world economy, such as the development of sectors that do not require heavy physical labor, in particular the service sector, and the transformation of the employment structure, have given impetus to the formation and development of female labor migration, which has become an important part of global labor migration. The most important principle of feminization is that women migrate not as escorts, but as the main earners of livelihoods. [6] Regardless of the reason for immigration, gender plays a key role in this. Risks, vulnerabilities and needs are also formed mainly depending on gender, being a boy or a girl, being a man or a woman significantly affects all aspects of the migration

process. While the terms “migrants and their families” and “men and their wives and children” were widely used in the 1960s and 1970s, the term “women’s migration” also appeared in research from the 1970s and 1980s. The main question regarding women’s migration during this period was whether migration modernized women and freed them from traditional values and behaviors. [7] According to statistical analyses, since 1990, there has been a growing trend in women’s participation in international migration processes, with the number of migrant women increasing year by year.[8] Nowadays, there are contexts about the problems that migrant women in different countries are facing or may face, the changes in society and the impact of migrant women on their children.[9] According to reports from the International Organization for Migration, today the share of men in migration is 52%, and the share of women is 48%. Whatever the driving force behind migration, shared ancestry and culture, including language, religion, customs and norms of behavior, often contribute to the difficulties of migration. It is also not easy to adapt to the worldview of another people. Migration is increasing due to the ease of movement and increasing opportunities among the peoples of the world. Accordingly, there is increasing debate about the benefits or harms of immigrants, and recently, economic fears, nationalism and xenophobia have increased across continents.

Most literature and empirical evidence suggests that immigrants bring economic benefits to the receiving country. However, cultural contamination, concerns about changing values and, more recently, the fear of terrorism make migration a dangerous process in the relations of countries. With the increase in migration, there is also an increase in the number of victims of human trafficking, which is a phenomenon both international and domestic. Commercial exploitation of persons usually takes the form of forced labor or sexual services and prostitution. Many also call it modern slavery. [10] According to information received from the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Uzbekistan through an official IOM appeal, in the first eleven months of 2023, 141 cases of human trafficking were registered and 193 victims of human trafficking were identified, of which 133 were women. [11]The recent increase in the proportion of women in migration accelerates this process. When women and girls migrate, they face 5 risks. 1) almost half of migrants are women, and half of refugees are women, 2) women are more exposed to great risks such as sexual exploitation, violence, and human trafficking, 3) women are subject to double discrimination both as migrants and as women. Today, xenophobia against immigration has developed in many countries. The media also talk about the harms that migrants bring rather than the economic benefits. 4) Women do not stop giving birth during their journey. Because most of them are women of childbearing age. Pregnancy and childbirth during irregular travel have a serious negative impact on their health, even leading to death. 5) Women and girls face more health problems both in their own country and in transit countries. The most important principle of feminization is that women migrate not as accompanying persons, but as the main earners of livelihood.[12]

As the scale of migration has expanded in Khorezm region, the proportion of women among them has also increased. As of May 1, 2024, the total population of Khorezm region is 1,995,589 people, of which 996,740 are women, and 469,657 are aged 30 and older. The total number of long-term migrants abroad in 2023 was 116,225 people, of which 86,182 were men and 30,043 were women. [13] Although the number of women is almost equal to the number of men, the share of women in migration is less than that of men. However, the impact of women's migration on society, family, and child rearing is high. Today, many scientific articles are being written by foreign researchers about women's migration and its impact on society and family. In particular, Hui Qiu, Xiao Liang, Dan Sun wrote that in China, sibling migration harms children left behind more than parental migration, especially girls. [14] Natalia Zotova, Victor Agadzhanian, Julia Isaeva, Tohir Kalandarov in their article “Worry, Work, Discrimination: A Psychologist's Socio-Ecological Model: Tensions among Central Asian Migrant Women in Russia” publish the results based on surveys conducted among migrants from Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan and Uzbekistan in the two largest Russian cities of Kazan and Nizhny Novgorod from April 2014 to February 2017. They write that remittances from migrants are an important source of external financing in many

developing countries.[15] Ellen Bal and other researchers have conducted research on the impact of women's reproductive and sexual health on women's reproductive and sexual health in the context of deep socio-economic, legal, cultural, and political challenges faced by female migrant workers in Dhaka, Bangladesh.[16] Sandra Simonsen writes in her article about the economic, cultural, and security challenges faced by migrants. She writes about Muslim migrants in Denmark who are reluctant to change their values and become part of Danish society, i.e., to adapt to the values and norms of the area they live in.[17] Marie-Rose Bashwiraa and Gemma van der Haarb describe how women artisans come to the mining areas of the eastern Democratic Republic of the Congo in search of economic security, security, and a new or better life. They provide insights into how women can find safety by coming here, despite the prevailing view of sexual violence against women. [18] Lynda Pickbourn writes in her article about the migration of women within national borders in Africa. In Ghana, she conducted fieldwork for a year and interviewed various groups of women. Among them were young, middle-aged, and older women who had returned home from migration for the planting season. Most of them were young, single, and childless, but she also wrote that there were many migrant women with one child. The study showed that since the 1980s, the increase in female migration from the northern region of Ghana was due to livelihood problems.[19] Browne C.V. and Brown K.L. write that the aging of the population in developed countries directly increases the need for skilled workers in long-term care, and these countries are turning to immigrant women to meet these needs. Currently, the demographic aging of our planet is developing at a rapid pace, affecting even developing countries. The number of people aged 65 and older among the world's population is growing 2.2 times faster than the total number. [20] In June 2021, a team of Samuel Hall researchers studied how migration shaped urban development and women's aspirations in the Shahrake Mahdia settlement in the Dashte Barchi district of Kabul. The situation in Herat provides insight into the impact of women's economic exclusion on society. Women are the backbone of the local economy, but new restrictions have prevented them from working outside the home.[21]

Although there is scientific research on gender relations in Uzbekistan, there are not many scientific works on women's migration and its specific aspects. At the level of the Khorezm region, this issue has not been studied. The factors causing the migration of Khorezm women have not been analyzed. In addition to external labor migration, there is also a process characteristic of the Khorezm region, which will directly affect the ethnic and demographic portrait of the region in the future. This is the increase in the number of women coming to Khorezm region from other regions for the purpose of marriage and starting a family. This topic requires separate study and expansion of research. In this article, we aim to present and highlight information on the causes and consequences of external migration of women in the Khorezm region.

Materials and methods.

According to the Agency for External Labor Migration, the number of Uzbek citizens temporarily employed abroad in 2022 is on average 2.4 million people. Of these, 568.5 thousand are women (24.1%), and 827.1 thousand (35.1%) are young people.[22] Migrants from Uzbekistan mainly go to Russia and Kazakhstan for work, followed by the Republic of Turkey, the Republic of South Korea, the United Arab Emirates, the European Union countries, and the United States. According to the World Bank, in 2017, 81% of male labor migrants from Uzbekistan and 67% of female labor migrants worked in Russia, 12% and 10% in Kazakhstan, and 3% and 18% in Turkey.[23] It can be seen that women are more likely to choose to work in Turkey. The reason for this is the high demand for domestic workers in Turkey. Migration from Khorezm to the Russian Federation is the most widespread. This is due to the gradual inclusion of women in the movement, an increase in the number of families arriving, the emergence of a generation of children born and raised in Russia, and the expansion of the geography of settlement.[24] Unlike other migration contexts, the number and percentage of women who migrate independently, rather than with family members, is increasing. Migration can empower women. First, educational opportunities. Through this, women and girls can gain access to

education and careers that are not available in their home countries. Second, they can benefit economically. This in turn affects their social engagement. Third, they can move from a previously dependent position to becoming financial contributors to their families by making regular remittances to their places of origin. This affects the well-being of their families and the place of women in the family.[25] First of all, economic reasons, i.e. family well-being, housing, weddings, etc. are the main reasons for women's migration. In addition, due to the fact that the Khorezm region is located in an ecologically unfavorable area, many people change their places of residence and work through internal and external migration. According to estimates, about 2 million people live in the most badly affected regions of Uzbekistan (Aral Sea area and Fergana Valley). Data are available to prove that these people have serious health problems, and that infant mortality rate increased dramatically in the early 90s (from 40 to 100 per 1000 born), and that there is a steep increase in the number of people with tuberculosis. Before the 1990s areas near the Aral and Caspian Seas had been used for subsurface nuclear tests, and since the 50s till the late 80s the Aral Sea territory hosted soviet military testing-sites for chemical and biological weapons, and the consequences of these activities for human health and the environment have not been studied yet. Women, more often (34.7%) than men (17.2%) changed their place of residence. This fact is connected with marriage traditions: a woman must live in her husband's family, and this often entails the change of abode.[26] As a result of the drying up of the Aral Sea, the deterioration of the land reclamation, the increase in the amount of salt in the water, and the spread of forests, the health of the region's population has deteriorated, cardiovascular, gastrointestinal, respiratory and skin diseases have increased. Between 1998 and 2008, the number of disabled women and children has increased sixfold. Anemia is rampant among children and women. After the economic factor, such environmental factors can be cited as the reason for external labor migration in Khorezm. In January-December 2020, the number of immigrants in the region amounted to 5.0 thousand people, and the number of emigrants was 10.7 thousand people. The migration balance is minus 5.7 thousand people. The high level of migration balance was recorded in the districts of Hazorasp (minus 1.1 thousand people), Qoshkopir (minus 0.9 thousand people), and Shavot (minus 0.6 thousand people).[27]

Why do women in Khorezm region want to work abroad? Is it a choice or an obligation? In order to get answers to these questions, a field study was conducted based on interviews with persons responsible for women's issues and chairmen of 10 MFYs (Mahalla Citizens' Assembly. A self-government system that exists in all regions, cities, and districts of Uzbekistan, where you can get the most reliable information about citizens) located in 10 MFYs in Khorezm region. The information obtained as a result of the study can serve as a basis for studying the causes and consequences of women's migration in Khorezm region.

Results

A number of data on women's migration were identified through a study of the literature, interviews, and information obtained from relevant agencies. Official data from authorized bodies will help shed light on the issue. The opinions of a number of respondents who participated in the interviews allow us to draw general conclusions.

The respondent expressed his reaction to women's migration on the example of a migrant family in Yangibazar district. In this household, a young family left their 2 minor children with their in-laws for house renovations. After a few months, the young migrant family decided to divorce. As it turned out from the interview, the reason for the divorce was jealousy. More precisely, in the rented house where they lived as migrants, there were other tenants besides the couple, and he was a man. The wife, on duty, prepares food and writes a notice to invite that man to dinner. When she sees this, her husband starts a fight and raises his hand. After that, he returns to his bride's house, but does not live well and goes to his father's house with his 2 children. Currently, they are divorced and 2 minor children are orphans. The neighborhood chairman's conclusion on this is that it is good to earn money by working abroad, but the living conditions there, getting acquainted with a different culture, and adapting to a new environment psychologically exhaust a

person. As a result, one can give in to emotions and make risky decisions for oneself and one's family. In fact, if people live contentedly, there is an opportunity to earn good money in Uzbekistan. It is better for women to adhere to Uzbek values and traditions and engage in raising their children, which is their main task. Their emigration abroad undermines the strength of the family. Such cases are actually very common. Also, the widespread opinion about migrant women in society is related to the idea that they choose an easy life. Is this really the case? It is possible that such a category exists among them, but most women actually choose to become migrants due to economic difficulties and the inability to find suitable jobs in their own country. A few years ago, the view of migrant women was negative. As the number of migrant women in society increases, this stereotype is changing. Today, however, as a result of such situations, the number of family breakups is increasing. It is well known that in the Uzbek mentality and values, the family is sacred and its disruption is considered a negative situation. However, in other respects, although women's migration occurs due to economic difficulties, it should not be understood as a means of livelihood. Despite the fact that they have sufficient financial resources to live, they do not stop living and working as migrants in different countries.[28]

The activist of the Bo'ston MFY Women's Union in Khiva district provided information about female migrants. A total of 1,811 women live in the neighborhood. 148 citizens are labor migrants abroad. Of these, 4 families are married couples. One of the youngest migrant families worked in the Russian Federation for 7 years to get married, came to Uzbekistan and got married, and after starting a family, took her husband with her. After going to Russia, the woman found out that her husband had a wife and one child, and came to Uzbekistan and filed for divorce. In conclusion, the respondent expressed the opinion that young people should make good use of the opportunities created by our state and contribute to the development of their country. She expressed the opinion that a man or a woman who migrates is tested in every way, and if they cannot withstand these difficulties, the family will be damaged. The distance between a husband and wife creates distrust between them. Arguments arise spontaneously and negatively affect the child's psychological state and future, regardless of who they stay with.[29]

Information provided by the Women's activist of the Qadriyat mahalla of the Qoshkopir district: As of April 1, 2024, there were 217 migrants, 26 of whom are women. One of the migrant women lost her husband in 2015. She has 3 children and, being the sole breadwinner of the family, went to St. Petersburg, the Russian Federation, to work in May 2023. According to the respondent, the most common reasons for women to migrate are related to weddings and housing construction. In Uzbekistan, lavish weddings require a lot of money, as a result, the head of a young family tries to make up for the lost money by going abroad to work alone or with his spouse. It is necessary to reduce excessive expenses during wedding ceremonies while preserving our values. The various rituals that begin a week before the wedding involve a large number of guests, expenses, and a negative impact on the economic situation of the wedding family. In the end, young people choose labor migration.[30]

Information from the chairman of the Iqbol MFY of the Qoshkopir district. There are a total of 143 emigrant citizens in the mahalla, and he provided information about one of them. This woman is a Russian language teacher with a higher education. The respondent stated that there are more and more women with higher education who are ready to work abroad in jobs that do not require qualifications. Many measures are being taken to reduce female labor migration, but such measures seem to be ineffective. The reason is that when talking to women working abroad by phone, they do not talk about returning to Uzbekistan and say that they are abroad to overcome economic difficulties.[31]

Urgench city Jingovuz MFY Women's activist provided information about another migrant family. There are 3 households in the house, a total of 18 citizens. The eldest son in the family died in 2010, his widow has been a labor migrant since 2012, she has one son, leaving him in the care of his mother and mother-in-law and working in Turkey. There she met a man and raised one child. During her childhood in Uzbekistan, she did not attend classes and could not master

subjects, so she skipped classes and graduated from school at the age of 19. There were complaints about problems in her upbringing. The woman had a car accident in Turkey, and her common-law husband abandoned his wife in a difficult situation, thus severing ties. Currently, she and her son are labor migrants in the Russian Federation.[32]

Statistical data show that being a single woman is a factor that increases women's migration. Women who are not married, divorced or whose spouse has died often express a desire to migrate. As a result of the interviews, the information provided to us by the responsible employees, based on the situation in their MFA, was dominated by an opinion against women's migration. Almost all of them believe that it is desirable for women to live and work in their own country, while raising children. According to the data, the total number of long-term migrants in Khorezm region in 2023 was 116,225 thousand, of which 86,182 were men and 30,043 were women. The number of people returning from long-term migration was 325,395, of which 248,454 were men and 76,941 were women. According to the purpose of their departure, 112,111 were for work, 608 for study, 3,502 for other purposes, and 4 for unknown purposes. Those who left for a period of 3 to 6 months were 6,268, 1,977 from 6 months to 1 year, 45,363 from 1 to 3 years, and 62,617 for a period of more than 3 years. Those who left for a period of more than 3 years accounted for the largest share. By age, there are 4,347 people under the age of 18, 29,427 people from 18 to 30, 52,867 people from 30 to 45, and 29,584 people over the age of 45. It is clear that the most active age range is between 30 and 45. This is the perinatal period of young women, that is, the age of having children and having children. During this period, most mothers leave their children with guardians. Upon return, 25,279 people underwent a medical examination in 2023, of which 18,369 were men and 6,910 were women. By April 1, 2024, 16,401 people underwent a medical examination, of which 11,892 were men and 4,509 were women. Infectious diseases in 2023-2024, 568, of which 16 were AIDS, 25 tuberculosis, 82 venereal diseases, 445 other infectious diseases.

In 2023, 129 were employed, 93 men and 36 women. By April 1, 2024, 481 citizens who returned from migration were provided with jobs. Of these, 287 were men and 194 were women. There were also 5,304 people who refused a job offer in 2023, 4,158 of whom were men and 1,146 were women. By May 1, 2024, 2,937 people, of which 2,139 were men and 858 were women, returned from labor migration from various countries and refused to work in Uzbekistan. As of April 2024, 13,435 women in the region left for the Russian Federation for a long time. As a result of preventive measures taken by the relevant employees of the Internal Affairs bodies, 3,406 women returned to their places of residence, 10,095 remain in Russia. Of the remaining 9,632, or 95.4 percent, left for work, 137, or 1.4 percent, for study, 8, or 0.1 percent, for treatment, and 318, or 3.2 percent, for other purposes. 68.9 percent of women returning from long-term migration underwent a medical examination. 103 were included in a special register. (In Uzbekistan, youth, women, and iron registers have been introduced to provide state assistance to the population in need of social protection), 44 were provided with material assistance. 12 were employed, 4 were sent to monocenters (monocenters called "Ishga Marhamat" have been established in Uzbekistan, where vocational training and foreign language courses are provided free of charge to the unemployed population).

During the special operational preventive event "Migration Prevention", information was obtained on the work carried out by women's issues inspectors with women who had gone abroad (to hotbed countries).

During the event, as of April 1, 2024, 480 women who were in hotbed countries were identified.

Total women traveling abroad	Total 480	Those who returned to their place of residence during the event	309
Ukraine	43	Ukraine	21

Egypt	11	Egypt	7
Tajikistan	33	Tajikistan	21
Kyrgyzstan	248	Kyrgyzstan	177
Turkmenistan	145	Turkmenistan	83

4 died in different countries, 2 are under special search, 6 are citizens of other regions, and 21 have returned to their places of residence and left for other countries. Currently, women from the Khorezm region in the hotbed countries are 7 in Ukraine, 1 in Egypt, 2 in Tajikistan, 68 in Kyrgyzstan, and 58 in Turkmenistan.[33]

Discussion

Today, significantly more children are being born in Uzbekistan than in the early 1990s (1991-1993), when the annual number of live births exceeded 700,000 for the first time. Until the mid-2010s, reproductive potential – taking into account the number and age composition of Uzbek women, as well as their fertility rate – grew almost continuously.[34] Such growth encourages labor migration of men and women abroad. According to statistics, in Uzbekistan, external labor migration is high in families with many children. The eldest child in the family also chooses or is forced to choose to become a labor migrant for his or her brothers and sisters when he or she reaches adulthood.

In the Khorezm region, women also migrate mainly for economic, followed by environmental and social reasons. As a result of interviews, the information provided to us by the responsible employees, based on the situation in their MFA, was dominated by the opinion against women's migration. Almost all of them believe that it is better for women to live and work in their own country, while raising children. Migration from the region to work abroad is the highest, followed by study and other reasons. As can be seen from the statistics, the most active age group is between 30 and 45 years old. This is the perinatal period of young women, that is, the age of having children and having children. During this period, most mothers leave their children with guardians. It is precisely children who suffer from migration. There are many problems associated with their stay with guardians or simply in the care of relatives. Reports show that migrants who returned to their homeland were medically examined and found to be infected with various infectious diseases. Women who traveled to hotbed countries were also identified, and a certain percentage of them still remain in those countries. Such situations are a threat to the national security and peace of the state. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 1, 2017 “On measures to radically improve the activities of internal affairs bodies in the field of migration processes and citizenship registration”,[35] On December 26, 2018, the "On the ratification of the Constitution of the International Organization for Migration (Brussels, October 19, 1953)"[36] The adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of July 5, 2018 “On additional measures to further improve the external labor migration system of the Republic of Uzbekistan”, the organization of the activities of the Fund for Supporting Persons Working Abroad and Protecting Their Rights and Interests, the radical improvement of the activities of internal affairs bodies in the field of migration processes and citizenship registration, and other organizational work are being established and being implemented.[37] At the same time, a new Committee on Women and Gender Equality has been established within the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which is engaged in harmonizing international standards in national legislation on ensuring women's rights and eliminating any form of discrimination. It is a fact that the Head of our state, in his Address to the Oliy Majlis, assigned the Committee to ensure women's employment, especially to provide 13 thousand women in difficult social situations with work and 1,600 women with housing, and the Committee has set clear plans and is carrying out practical work in this regard. In September 2019, the Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men" and "On Protection of Women from Harassment and Violence" were adopted. On May 1, 2019, the “Women's

Entrepreneurship Centers”, which have the status of a non-governmental non-profit organization, were established. In short, many activities are being carried out to implement women's rights and freedoms, as well as equal labor rights. There is also a task to return women who are labor migrants abroad to their places of residence, and opportunities are being created for them to find comfortable jobs and do business in their homeland.

Conclusion.

In the Khorezm region, economic reasons are the main driving force behind women's migration, followed by environmental and social reasons. In addition to economic reasons such as unemployment, poverty, debt, lack of housing, and need, social factors such as family disagreements, divorces, and women's aspirations for themselves and their children to receive education and development also contribute to the development of this direction of migration. While female labor migration creates positive opportunities for its participants, such as earning an income, solving economic problems, and professional growth, it also creates the conditions for them to become victims of human trafficking, sexual violence, discrimination, and harassment.[38] Although women face greater risks when they migrate than men, women's migration also has a number of positive features. First, it is an opportunity for education, secondly, economic benefits, and thirdly, it is a way to transform from a previously useless woman into a useful woman with a place in the family by becoming a financial provider. When it comes to the negative consequences of women's migration, it is primarily seen in the shortcomings in child rearing. In response to the regional and global situation regarding children affected by migration, the European Union has established a partnership with UNICEF to find solutions to the problems of protecting children affected by migration in eight countries, including Uzbekistan. A survey was conducted in 1,000 households with the direct participation of 200 trained professionals in Bukhara, Fergana, Surkhandarya and Khorezm regions. Many migrant families (45 percent) have at least two children left in the care of guardians; Family members, especially mothers, often leave children under the age of 6 and migrate. These years are considered a critical period in children's development; they are considered a period of establishing relationships with parents; about 37 percent of children live in the care of relatives; 12 percent are deprived of benefits; 3 percent are called crazy, lazy, and similar words; 8 percent of children are treated rudely; parental migration negatively affects the emotional state of children 33 percent of children consider themselves unhappy; 21 percent live in constant anxiety; 44 percent of children said that they want to talk about their feelings with their mothers, and that caregivers do not understand them as much as their mothers; and caregivers who participated in the survey reported that half of the children become stubborn and unruly; 7 percent of children said that physical punishment by caregivers further reduces their mood; The survey concluded that children's emotional problems increase and extreme cases of suicide may occur due to the lack of care, support and protection. A child is spiritually connected to his mother until the age of 12, and it is during this period that it is very important for the mother to be with the child. If a mother leaves her child alone at this age, the characteristics of a simple child such as stubbornness and stubbornness, not listening to anyone, increase, and stubborn children grow up to be unable to express their desires and have low self-esteem. The mother's role in the child's mental well-being is considered higher than that of the father. If a child is left without both a mother and a father at this age, this will lead to great psychological trauma in the future.[39]

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